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ITALIAN CLASSIFICATION METHOD FOR MACROINVERTEBRATES IN LAKES METHOD SUMMARY

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Italian classification method for macroinvertebrates in lakes

Method summary

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Benthic Quality Index for Italian Lakes

6.1. Introduction

An important step has been taken by the European Union in 2000 with the launching of the Water Framework Directive (WFD - 2000/60/CE; EU, 2000) defining the ecological status as an expression of the structure and functioning of all types of aquatic ecosystems. As a consequence, the classification of the ecological status of each system should consider changes in the structure and the function of the biological communities and of the whole ecosystem in response to different anthropogenic pressures. The Water Framework Directive has established the general principles and a framework for Community action in the field of water, in other words the assessment of ecological status of water bodies should be derived through the use of numerical indices developed on mandatory Biological Quality Elements (BQE), and comparing the values obtained in a site with the ones of a reference site through the use of the Ecological Quality Ratio (EQR).

To ensure that the legislation is correctly applied it is essential to link the presence of selected species to a well-defined range of environmental quality conditions. The process requires a thorough knowledge of at least the taxonomy of chironomids and oligochaetes, the two main macroinvertebrate groups inhabiting lakes, and of their autoecology, to define sensitive and tolerant species to different anthropogenic pressures. This is the essential premise to identify indicator species and for the development of quality indices. The BQEs considered in lakes are: phytoplankton, diatoms, macrophytes, macroinvertebrates and fish.

This report includes the description of the index and the data on lacustrine macroinvertebrates considered, which the WFD requires is assessed through its i) taxonomic composition (community structure), ii) abundance, iii) diversity and iv) the presence of tolerant/sensitive taxa. Eutrophication is regarded as significant anthropogenic pressure, because since the '50s a large number of Italian lakes suffered an increase in eutrophication, as a result of human pressures (Premazzi et al., 2003).

It is generally known that, since the '70s, macroinvertebrates were recommended in water quality monitoring and for establishing water quality criteria, because they are ubiquitous, they reflect changes in the freshwater habitats they inhabit, they include a wide spectrum of species and a wide range of responses to different environmental stress, they are sedentary, they show a well-defined spatial structure, they have relatively long life-cycles and are pretty easy to sample (Rosenberg & Resh, 1993). Direct anthropogenic impacts (like presence of infrastructures, industrial and domestic sewages, etc) alter the status of waters with effects on the structure and function of the biota (Rosenberg & Resh, 1993).

Sampling protocol

The sampling protocol was derived from US-EPA methodologies for soft sediments (<http://www.epa.gov/owow/monitoring>).

In lakes, where an obvious depth gradient exists, sampling strategy may be carried out in the form of a stratified sampling, working on transects with sampling sites arranged to give equal coverage of the different habitats and different depths. Each sampling site is located along transects connecting the shore-line to the maximum depth, covering three main areas differing in depth (littoral, sublittoral and profundal). Each sample consists of 3 grab replicates per site (minimum effort to obtain a good data set) for a total of 9 replicates in a transect. Sampling is performed using a grab with an area of 0.0225 m² of lake bottom.

The number of transects depends on lake area (Table 1) and their position is based on expert knowledge (e.g. most representative sites for each water body: different sediment texture, presence of inflow/outflow rivers and of human impacts, variability of the shore-line habitat, low slope of the

banks), but it is mainly based on calculation. The sampling period is from February to April (Spring) and from September to October (Autumn) (i.e. during mixing and stratification periods), according to insects' life-cycles.

Tab. 1 - Relation between lake surface area and number of transects, of sampling sites and of replicates.

Lake area (km ²)		No transects	No stations	No replicates	Examples
	≤0,5	1	3	9	
0.6	2.9	2	6	18	
3.0	6.5	3	9	27	
6.6	11.9	4	12	36	
12	19	5	15	45	
20	31	6	18	54	
32	49	7	21	63	Lugano
50	75	8	24	72	Bracciano, Iseo
76	115	9	27	81	
116	174	10	30	90	Bolsena, Como
175	262	11	33	99	Maggiore
263	395	12	36	108	Garda

The collected samples washed through a 250 µm mesh size sieving net to eliminate the sediment finest fractions are then preserved with formalin (5%) in plastic bottles. The sample treatment in the lab includes the sorting of the whole sample under a stereo-microscope and the subdivision of the organisms into main taxonomic groups. The specimens are identified to species level, whenever possible. The genus level is considered when the available material (presence of immature or poorly preserved specimens) hinders species identification. Numbers are expressed as individuals per 1 m² (ind m⁻²), dividing the total abundance of each species in a sample by the sampling area.

For a detailed description of the sampling strategy and of sample processing see the national guidelines (Boggero et al., 2013 on the CNR-ISE Web page at <http://www.ise.cnr.it/wfd> as *Macroinvertebrati - Aggiornamento 2013*).

Standardisation of methodologies refer to:

- ISO 5667-4. 1987. Water quality. Sampling – Part 4: Guidance on sampling from lakes, natural and man-made.
- ISO 9391. 1993. Water quality. Sampling in deep waters for macro-invertebrates. Guidance on the use of colonization, qualitative and quantitative samplers: 13 pp.
- ISO 10870. 2012. Water quality. Guidelines for the selection of sampling methods and devices for benthic macroinvertebrates in fresh waters: 24 pp.
- UNI EN ISO 5667-1. Qualità dell'acqua, Campionamento - Parte 1: Linee guida per la definizione dei programmi e delle tecniche di campionamento.

Italian National Index (Benthic Quality Index for Italian Lakes)

In view of the marked incidence of eutrophication on lake waters, Italy has decided to consider the trophic status as the main pressure to be addressed. The response of the benthic macroinvertebrates

to hydromorphological alterations will be taken into account in the next future when data will be available.

The Benthic Quality Index elaborated can be used in all types of lakes, placed in continental and insular Italy, with conductivity $< 2.5 \text{ mS cm}^{-1}$, and it is currently used to classify the status of lakes with average depth higher than 15 m. The Index cannot be applied to brackish or mesohaline lakes with conductivity higher than the indicated threshold, as they are likely inhabited by a very different benthic community.

The index is calculated considering different sensitivity values for different species. The authors decided to focus mainly on Chironomids and Oligochaetes, as they are the main components of the macroinvertebrate lake community, being other taxonomic groups less represented.

Among the 18 lake types described in the national document (Buraschi et al., 2005), the index has been applied to lakes belonging to eight different types (AL-2, A-3, AL-4, AL-5, AL-6, AL-8, AL-9, AL-10) located in the Subalpine Region and four types in the Mediterranean Region (ME-2, ME-3, ME-4, ME-5). These lakes (36 in the Subalpine Region and 7 in the Mediterranean Region) are mainly located at elevations below 800 m s.l.m. Part of them have average depth $< 15 \text{ m}$ (AL-2, AL-4, AL-5, AL-8, AL-10, ME-2, ME-3), and part $> 15 \text{ m}$ (AL-3, AL-6, AL-9, ME-4, ME-5).

The data used derive from national monitoring sampling campaigns and from research projects (like LIFE+ INHABIT 08/ENV/IT/000413). A detailed description of the index (Rossaro et al., 2013) and the notes from filling the common excel sheet can be found on the CNR-ISE Web page at <http://www.ise.cnr.it/wfd> as *Manuale 2013* and as *Guida alla compilazione*. The index has still to be intercalibrated.

Following the methodologies proposed by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 1982 – Tab. 2) on trophic classification of lakes only two lakes among those with mean depth higher than 15 m (profundal lakes) show values for Total Phosphorous (mg m^{-3}), Chlorophyll *a* (mg m^{-3}), and Transparency (m) characteristic of oligotrophic lakes.

Tab. 2 - Class limits for the OECD chemico-physical parameters for different lake trophic categories.

Lake types	TP	Chl a	Trasparency
	mg m^{-3}		m
Ultra-oligotrophic	≤ 4.0	≤ 1.0	≥ 12
Oligotrophic	≤ 10.0	≤ 2.5	≥ 6
Mesotrophic	10-35	2.5-8	6-3
Eutrophic	35-100	8-25	3 - 1.5
Ipereutrophic	≥ 100	≥ 25	≤ 1.5

The results allow to highlight as reference sites those waterbodies who experienced all chemico-physical values in the range of oligotrophic lakes following OECD prescription, like Lake Mergozzo and Lake Weißensee in Austria on which no relevant impacts are present (Tab. 3). These two waterbodies show also high profundal mean oxygen % saturation values. Information about Lake Mergozzo shall be found in Fornaroli et al. (2015).

The remaining four Austrian lakes for which chemical and biological information were available, were not considered because their data sets refer to species not present on the Italian territory and therefore, the percent density of species with known indicator weight doesn't represent the requested 75% of the total density of all species present at a site.

Tab. 3 – Chemico-physical values of the different lakes following the OECD trophic classification.

	O2_hypolimnic	TP	Chl a	Trasparency
	%	mg m-3	mg m-3	m
	mean values in deep layers	median values at mixing	median values	median values
Braies	47	8	4.00	3.92
Como	61	40	2.50	5.50
Iseo	11	97	5.80	3.25
Levico	26	24	2.70	6.25
Liscia	15	37	6.68	2.90
Mergozzo	75	4	1.94	8.25
Mezzola	61	13	6.80	2.45
Monate	6	7	2.90	7.75
Montespluga	82	13	1.40	4.50
Posada	32	50	6.81	1.55
Sirio	3	81	3.04	5.00
SosCanales	6	47	6.63	2.70
Viverone	59	169	1.75	4.00
Weißensee	90	5	1.55	9.06

Formulation of the BQIES Index

Data required

Abundance of each taxon (ind m⁻²) obtained from an integrated sample of 3 replicates/site taken in an area of 225 cm² (for a total area of 225 * 3 = 675 cm²) in the littoral, sub-littoral and profundal zones on soft substrates, in at least two field campaigns in the same year (preferably at the overturn and after the summer stratification).

Procedure

1. The proposed index was developed and applied on historical (1953 - 2008) and more recent data belonging to 36 lakes sampled by grab in soft sediments (see Appendix A for list of lakes and periods). Only the species present in at least 5% of samples in all the lakes were considered, taking account of the two samplings required by the protocol. In this way, all the species useful for bioindication were included (Tables 4 and 5).
2. The index used is mainly an index of trophic, and as such it has been constructed with the aim of linking the response of macroinvertebrates to physical-chemical factors connected with trophic, i.e. oxygen saturation percentage, transparency (measured by Secchi disk) and total phosphorus. It is based on the calculation of indicators weights (sensitivity values) of the

different species. The indicators weights are obtained calculating the Shannon Diversity Index (SDI) at the various sites.

3. It is based on the principle that, assuming a normal distribution of the observations, the optimum value of the species along a gradient coincides with the weighted average (Ter Braak & Prentice, 1988). Instead of calculating the optimal response to a chemical gradient, the optimal response to a gradient of biodiversity was evaluated. It assumed that species living preferably in sites characterised by high biodiversity are indicative of good environmental quality. On the contrary, species living preferably in sites characterised by low biodiversity are indicative of altered environments. The average of the SDIs was calculated using all values derived from sites where the species was present, weighting the values on the abundances of the species, according to the formula:

$$\bar{z}_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \log_{10}(y_{ij} + 1) * z_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n \log_{10}(y_{ij} + 1)}$$

where:

z_i = Shannon Diversity Index measured in a station i ,

y_{ij} = abundance of species j in the same sampling station,

\bar{z}_j = optimum value for the species j

The weighted averages can be interpreted as optimum values for each species (Ter Braak & Prentice, 1988) and used as weights (BQIW - Benthic Quality Index Weight) to be assigned to each species in applying the Benthic Quality Index. Having multi-year data for the same lake, each year has been considered per se.

Tab. 4 - Indicator weights for the macroinvertebrate taxa. BQIW: indicator weight of each species.

Taxa groups	Species	Abbreviation	BQIW
Platyhelminthes	<i>Dugesia tigrina</i>	D_tigrina	0,649
	<i>Planaria torva</i>	P_torva	0,473
	<i>Polycelis nigra</i>	P_nigra	1,000
Naididae	<i>Amphichaeta</i> sp.	Amphichaeta	0,755
	<i>Aulodrilus pluriseta</i>	A_pluriseta	0,645
	<i>Aulophorus</i> sp.	Aulophorus	0,738
	<i>Bichaeta sanguinea</i>	B_sanguinea	0,580
	<i>Bothrioneurum vejvodskyanum</i>	B_vejvodskyanum	0,651
	<i>Branchiura sowerbii</i>	B_sowerbyi	0,494
	<i>Chaetogaster langi</i>	C_langi	0,787
	<i>Dero digitata</i>	D_digitata	0,616
	<i>Embolocephalus velutinus</i>	E_velutinus	0,537
	<i>Ilyodrilus templetoni</i>	I_templetoni	0,387
	<i>Limnodrilus claparedeianus</i>	L_claparedeianus	0,437
	<i>Limnodrilus hoffmeisteri</i>	L_hoffmeisteri	0,416
	<i>Limnodrilus</i> spp.	Limnodrilus	0,412
	<i>Limnodrilus udekemianus</i>	L_udekemianus	0,712
	<i>Nais communis</i>	N_communis	0,589
	<i>Ophidonais serpentina</i>	O_serpentina	0,709
	<i>Potamotheix hammoniensis</i>	P_hammoniensis	0,481
	<i>Potamotheix</i> sp.	Potamotheix.sp	0,539
	<i>Potamotheix vejvodskyi</i>	P_vejvodskyi	0,523
	<i>Pristina</i> spp.	Pristina	0,736
	<i>Psammoryctides barbatus</i>	P_barbatus	0,458
	<i>Rhyacodrilus coccineus</i>	R_coccineus	0,737
	<i>Slavina appendiculata</i>	S_appendiculata	0,922
<i>Spirosperma ferox</i>	S_ferox	0,306	
<i>Stylaria lacustris</i>	S_lacustris	0,686	
<i>Tubifex tubifex</i>	T_tubifex	0,362	
<i>Uncinaxis uncinata</i>	U_uncinata	0,613	
<i>Vejvodskyella comata</i>	V_comata	0,882	
Haplotaxidae	<i>Haplotaxis gordioides</i>	H_gordioides	0,563
Lumbricidae	<i>Eiseniella tetraedra</i>	E_tetraedra	0,524
Lumbriculidae	<i>Lumbriculus variegatus</i>	L_variegatus	0,216
	<i>Stylodrilus heringianus</i>	S_heringianus	0,308
Hyrudinea	<i>Alboglossiphonia complanata</i>	G_complanata	0,794
	<i>Erpobdella octoculata</i>	E_octoculata	0,535
	<i>Helobdella stagnalis</i>	H_stagnalis	0,635
Crustacea	<i>Asellus aquaticus</i>	A_aquaticus	0,201
	<i>Echinogammarus stammeri</i>	E_stammeri	0,635
	<i>Niphargus foreli</i>	N_foreli	0,093
	<i>Synurella ambulans</i>	S_ambulans	0,537
Molluscs	<i>Acroloxus lacustris</i>	A_lacustris	0,402
	<i>Belgrandia latina</i>	B_latina	0,637
	<i>Bithynia tentaculata</i>	B_tentaculata	0,552
	<i>Dreissena polymorpha</i>	D_polymorpha	0,225
	<i>Euomphalia strigella</i>	E_strigella	0,732
	<i>Gyraulus albus</i>	G_albus	0,621
	<i>Physa acuta</i> (= <i>Physella acuta</i> , <i>Haitia acuta</i>)	P_acuta	0,550
	<i>Pisidium casertanum</i>	P_casertanum	0,418
	<i>Planorbis corneus</i>	P_corneus	0,396
	<i>Pyrgula annulata</i>	P_annulata	0,520
	<i>Sphaerium</i> sp.	Sphaerium	0,716
	<i>Theodoxus fluviatilis</i>	T_fluviatilis	0,692
	<i>Unio pictorum</i>	U_pictorum	0,533
	<i>Valvata piscinalis</i>	V_piscinalis	0,561
	<i>Viviparus ater</i>	V_ater	0,801

Tab. 5 - Indicator weights for insects. BQIW: indicator weight of each species.

Taxa groups	Species	Abbreviation	BQIW
Chironomidae	<i>Benthalia carbonaria</i> (=Einfeldia dissidens)	B_carbonaria	0.037
	<i>Chironomus</i> gr. <i>anthracinus</i>	C_anthracinus-gr	0.196
	<i>Chironomus</i> gr. <i>plumosus</i>	C_plumosus-gr	0.278
	<i>Cladopelma</i> spp.	C_laccophila-gr	0.445
	<i>Cladotanytarsus</i> spp.	C_atridorsum	0.609
	<i>Conchapelopia pallidula</i>	C_pallidula	0.643
	<i>Cricotopus</i> (<i>Isocladius</i>) <i>sylvestris</i>	I_sylvestris	0.563
	<i>Cricotopus</i> spp.	C_tremulus-gr	0.767
	<i>Cryptochironomus</i> spp.	C_supplicans	0.486
	<i>Cryptotendipes holsatus</i>	C_holsatus	0.394
	<i>Demicryptochironomus vulneratus</i>	D_vulneratus	0.595
	<i>Dicotendipes</i> spp.	D_lobiger	0.657
	<i>Endochironomus albipennis</i>	E_albipennis	0.639
	<i>Glyptotendipes</i> spp.	G_pallens	0.000
	<i>Hydrobaenus</i> spp.	H_distylus	0.195
	<i>Microchironomus tener</i>	M_tener	0.329
	<i>Microtendipes</i> spp.	M_pedellus	0.592
	<i>Orthocladus frigidus</i>	O_frigidus	0.797
	<i>Orthocladus</i> spp.	O_oblidens	0.751
	<i>Pagastiella orophila</i>	P_orophila	0.698
	<i>Parachironomus</i> spp.	Parachironomus	0.583
	<i>Paracladopelma</i> gr. <i>camptolabis</i>	P_camptolabis-gr	0.427
	<i>Parakiefferiella bathophila</i>	P_bathophila	0.703
	<i>Paralauterborniella nigrohalteralis</i>	P_nigrohalteralis	0.552
	<i>Paratanytarsus</i> spp.	P_mediterraneus	0.501
	<i>Paratendipes albimanus</i>	P_albimanus	0.593
	<i>Phaenopsectra flavipes</i>	P_flavipes	0.464
	<i>Polypedilum</i> (<i>Tripodura</i>) <i>scalaenum</i>	T_scalaenum	0.402
	<i>Polypedilum nubeculosum</i>	P_nubeculosum	0.613
	<i>Procladius chorues</i>	P_choreus	0.417
	<i>Prodiamesa olivacea</i>	P_olivacea	0.515
	<i>Psectrocladius sordidellus</i>	P_sordidellus-gr	0.666
	<i>Pseudochironomus prasinatus</i>	P_prasinatus	0.605
<i>Stempellina</i> spp.	S_minor	0.738	
<i>Stictochironomus</i> spp.	S_pictulus	0.670	
<i>Tanypus punctipennis</i>	T_punctipennis	0.305	
<i>Tanytarsus</i> spp.	T_gregarius-gr	0.325	
<i>Xenochironomus xenolabis</i>	X_xenolabis	0.717	
Diptera non-Chironomidae	Ceratopogonidae	Ceratopogon	0.173
	<i>Chaoborus flavicans</i>	C_flavicans	0.017
Heteroptera	<i>Micronecta minutissima</i>	M_minutissima	0.613
Ephemeroptera	<i>Caenis horaria</i>	C_horaria	0.354
	<i>Ephemera danica</i>	E_danica	0.463
Coleoptera	<i>Microcara testacea</i>	M_testacea	0.346
Megaloptera	<i>Sialis lutaria</i>	S_lutaria	0.133
Trichoptera	<i>Phryganea</i> sp.	Phryganea	0.270
	<i>Sericostoma</i> sp.	Sericostoma	0.421

4. The weighted averages were then rescaled between 1 and 0 using the following formula:

$$BQIW_j = \frac{(\bar{z}_j - \bar{z}_{\min j})}{(\bar{z}_{\max j} - \bar{z}_{\min j})}$$

where:

$BQIW_j$ = rescaled value of the indicator weight z_j

5. Then, the BQI_i for each station i were calculated, using the values of the BQIW_j weights according to the formula:

$$BQI_i = \frac{\sum_j^p BQIW_j * \log_{10}(y_{ij} + 1)}{\sum_j^p \log_{10}(y_{ij} + 1)}$$

where:

p = number of species of the station i

$BQIW_j$ = indicator weight of species j

y_{ij} = density (ind m⁻²) of species j at station i

BQI_i = Benthic Quality Index of the station i

The formula incorporates algorithms already used for the macroinvertebrate fauna (Wiederholm, 1976, 1980) with two major differences:

- the number of species involved is very high (currently 104, Tables 4 and 5)
- species are not only considered as species presence at each site, but also as densities (absolute abundances per each site).

By calculating the BQI (Rossaro et al., 2006, 2007), the total density of a site was not taken into account, as required by the WFD, therefore, a change to the BQI was applied, including also a measure of the total density (Rosenberg et al., 2004; Leonardsson et al., 2009).

By calculating the indicator weights, some authors used the rarefaction method to calculate the biodiversity (Sanders, 1968; Hurlbert, 1971; Magurran, 1988). The number of species expected in a sample was estimated, as if it was composed of a fixed number of individuals (e.g. 50 - called ES_{50} , Rosenberg et al., 2004). In our Index, although using the previously proposed idea (Sanders, 1968; Hurlbert, 1971; Magurran, 1988), some changes were applied. In particular, instead of using the diversity index based on the rarefaction method, we adopted the SDI, and instead of using the 5th percentile of the curve (Leonardsson et al., 2009), we used the weighted averages.

Furthermore, it should be noticed that only for a fraction p of the total m species present at a site the indicator weight is known. To take into consideration even the species for which the indicator weight is unknown, the Log₁₀ of the number of species present, and the ratio between the total density of individuals and the total density of individuals + 5 was included in the Index. The ratio is very close to 1 when the total density of a sample is high, and it becomes significantly < 1 when the sample is made up of few and rare individuals (Leonardsson et al.,

2009). The change is particularly important for samples containing few individuals: when two stations have the same species composition, the Index will be higher in the station with higher number of individuals. In this way, the total density of each sample was included in the Index, as required by the WFD:

$$BQIES_i = \left[\sum_{j=1}^p \left(\frac{\log_{10}(y_{ij} + 1)}{\sum_{j=1}^p \log_{10}(y_{ij} + 1)} * BQIW_j \right) \right] * \log_{10}(m + 1) * \left(\frac{\sum_{j=1}^m y_{ij}}{\sum_{j=1}^m y_{ij} + 5} \right)$$

where:

p = number of species for which the indicator weight ($BQIW_j$) is known

y_{ij} = density (ind m^{-2}) of species j at station i

m = total number of species present

6. After calculating the indicator weight of each species (calculated on the basis of the SDI), the Benthic Quality Index (BQIES) of the same 36 lakes used for the calculation of the indicator weights, was compared with the values of the parameters currently used for the trophic classification of lakes (transparency, total phosphorus at overturn, hypolimnetic oxygen percent during stratification – Law Decree 152/99) to assess the robustness of the indicator weights assigned.

Significant positive linear relationships ($P < 0.05$, Fig. 1 and Tab. 6) were identified with the hypolimnetic oxygen percent and with transparency, while a significant negative linear relationship ($P < 0.05$, Fig. 1 and Tab. 6) with the total phosphorus was found.

7. Then, the BQIES Index was calculated using the validated data belonging to the monitoring program (2009-2014) and the data relative to the lakes included in the Life + INHABIT project. Data were considered validated when:
 - macroinvertebrates were identified to genus/species level, at least for the two main groups (Chironomids and Oligochaetes),
 - have a twice per-year sampling frequency for each transect of each lake, as requested by the national sampling protocol (Boggero et al., 2013).

After validation, a dataset consisting of 8 lakes provided through national monitoring and 10 lakes through the INHABIT project was obtained. The BQIES Index data were plotted following their distribution with respect to the hypolimnetic oxygen percent during stratification. Among deep lakes, the results showed a good separation between lakes with poor and those with rather high oxygen concentrations in the profundal layers, even during the summer period (stratification) (Fig. 1 and Tab. 6). Consequently, it was confirmed that Lake Mergozzo and Lake Weißensee are reference even on the basis of the application of the BQIES index.

The application of this Index is to be considered valid only when the percent density of species with known indicator weight represents at least 75% of the total density of all species present at a site. Otherwise, the Index value is erroneous. The indicators weights, however robust, will be

subject to continuous monitoring and adjustment with the implementation of the original dataset, especially if the data belong to the Mediterranean Ecoregion, currently scarcely known.

Fig. 1 - Relationships between the BQIES Index of 36 Italian lakes and the different parameters considered by the Italian law for the trophic classification of lakes.

Tab. 6 - A) equations expressing the relationships between the chemical-physical parameters and the BQIES;
 B) R², degrees of freedom and parameters of the equations.

A		B		
$BQIES = b * O_2 + a$ $BQIES = b * trasp + a$ $BQIES = b * \log_{10}(TP + 1) + a$		O ₂ (mg l ⁻¹)	Trasp (m)	TP (mg l ⁻¹)
R ²		0,220	0,301	0,182
g.d.l.		36	36	36
b		0,023	0,038	0,157
a		0,195	0,117	-0,038

Fig. 2 - Relationships between the BQIES Index related only to deep lakes and their hypolimnetic oxygen content (percent saturation) during stratification.

Assessment of confidence intervals of WFD status class

Because of the reduced number of lakes available for the definition of the quality classes, a simplified procedure was used. The reference value has been chosen by averaging the values calculated on the two Italian lakes for which anthropic pressure is negligible.

Tab. 7 - Class limits for the Benthic Quality Index (BQIES)

Reference value	Class limits							
	High/Good		Good/Moderate		Moderate/Poor		Poor/Bad	
	Value	EQR	Value	EQR	Value	EQR	Value	EQR
0.525	0.46	0.88	0.40	0.76	0.33	0.63	0.26	0.50

The obtained value (0.40) represents the threshold separating the class "good" from the lower classes. Then, the other class limits were chosen so as to divide the remaining interval into equal parts, as indicated in table 7.

Use of the BQIES Index

Data required

- 1) Fill in the sampling campaign form in the Appendix of the national sampling protocol,
- 2) After sorting, taxonomic identification and counting of each individual species/species group, fill in the form in the Appendix of the laboratory protocol (Boggero et al., 2011);
- 3) densities of each taxon assessed from an integrated sample of 3 replicates/depth layer collected in littoral, sub-littoral and profundal depth layers, respectively, on soft substrate, in at least two sampling campaigns carried out in the same year (preferably at the overturn and during summer stratification) for a useful area of 225 cm² (and for a total area of 225 * 3 = 675 cm²).

Procedure

- 1) The data obtained from the three replicates/depth layer have to be averaged to provide a sufficiently representative picture of the density of each species in the study area. Remember to calculate the average about the 3 replicates, even if in a replicate no species was found;
- 2) Apply the BQIES Index multiplying the density of each species/group of species for their own indicator weight, and calculate the ratio with the total density. The results have to be multiplied by the Log10 of the total number of species present +1 and by the ratio of the density of each species, without associated indicator weight, to the total density of species without indicator weight + 5;
- 3) The Index have to be applied for each depth layer, and for each transect positioned within a lake;
- 4) The total BQIES Index for each depth layer is the average of the individual values of BQIES calculated for the same depth layer;
- 5) The total BQIES Index for each lake is the average of the individual values of BQIES calculated for the three depth layers.

Conclusions

Currently, the BQIES Index is a useful tool for the ecological assessment of the quality of deep Italian lakes. The index includes all types of lakes, and does not presents type-specific reference sites.

The Index proposed cannot be considered definitive, as new species with different autoecology could potentially be collected in lakes currently not sampled. The indicators weights listed in tables 2 and 3 have to be updated as monitoring proceeds. The taxonomic level required is highly detailed (species/species group), at least for Oligochaetes and Chironomids, as previous studies have shown a wide range of responses among species of the same genus, family or class. Grouping species in upper ranks (genus level), there is a risk to obtain groups that include tolerant and sensitive species. By contrast, knowing the response of individual species to different environmental factors is pivotal when there is the need to separate the effects of pollution by the effect of natural factors on the structure of communities. It seemed that a taxonomic resolution higher than the species/species group level has a low indicator power.

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